

III. Tuşnad Eco Bear
conf
Book of Abstracts

22-23 October 2024
Băile Tuşnad
Romania

III. TusnadEcoBear Conference Contacts

Organiser: István Imecs
E-mail: imecs.istvan17@gmail.com

Scientific coordinators:

Cristian-Remus Papp, PhD
E-mail: cristian.papp@ubbcluj.ro

Nándor Erős, PhD Student
E-mail: erosnandi@gmail.com

Moderator: Radu Pirca
E-mail: radu.pirca@wall-street.ro

Edited by: Nándor Erős

E-mail: erosnandi@gmail.com

Revised by: Members of TusnadEcoBear Team

III. TusnadEcoBear Conference

22 - 23 October 2024
Băile Tuşnad, Romania

Welcome Address

A conference about people and bears, about coexistence.

The aim of the conference is to bring together a variety of views, competences and experiences from various experts from Europe and beyond, on the topic of human-large carnivore coexistence. The discussions shall foster the generation of practical and viable solutions for reducing human-wildlife conflicts in human dominated landscapes. The conference seeks to identify the current level of knowledge regarding the management of brown bear populations across Europe, as well as best and negative practices. The interaction between key international experts and young participants is highly encouraged in order to build capacity in terms of coping with future challenges (including the ones derived from climate change).

The conference is organised as part of the CERV project (101146879) "Coexisting with bears - Conservation needs Conversation!" funded by the European Union and implemented with the support of the ProjectBag Association (Destination Management Unit - Băile Tuşnad and Surroundings), Mayor's Office of Băile Tuşnad and WWF-Romania. The conference is supported by the Nature FIRST project (101060954), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program.

Respectfully,

TusnadEcoBear Team

Funded by
the European Union

Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV)
Coexisting with bears Conservation needs Conversation!

CERV COEXISTENCE – PROJECT SUMMARY

Across EU member states, large-carnivore management is becoming increasingly challenging as both human safety and the conservation of wildlife populations have to be considered. There is a lack of a clear long-term vision for achieving and maintaining coexistence between humans and bears in many Eastern European countries, where human-bear conflicts are frequent. Rural communities are those actually affected and often ignored by the state authorities and other relevant stakeholders when it comes to establishing and implementing coexistence management plans. Therefore this project aims to foster participatory decision-making and collaborative management among the key stakeholders from 3 pilot countries (Romania, Bulgaria, Hungary) under the umbrella of academic knowledge and guidance (Austria) while promoting and ensuring active community engagement (local/regional community and general public) to provide guidelines for sustainable coexistence plans that go beyond changing political positions of local and state authorities. Thus, the project seeks to foster a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for brown bear conservation. Special attention will be paid to youth education and engagement to increase understanding, knowledge about human-bear conflict and the species management, while building empathy and support for bears in the upcoming decision-making generation. At present, policy debates and decision-making processes around coexistence with bears are conducted with a poor share of democratic/intercultural competence in traditionally patriarchal societies, thus the project targets the pro-active participation of marginalized groups such as women and ethnic and religious minorities. Lessons learned and best practices will be shared at the national and European levels and it will make sure that activities implemented remain operative and efficient after the project ends. This project contributes substantially to the implementation of EU and national policies.

Project financed by the European Union. The views and opinions expressed are entirely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Union, which cannot be held responsible for them. **CONSENT FOR THE PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA** The operators of personal data are: Association WWF Romania and Association Cutia de Proiecte – Project Bag in partnership with Băile Tușnad City Hall. The purpose of the processing: conducting and promoting the project entitled "Coexistence with bears – Conservation needs conversation!", monitoring the fulfillment of its objectives, implementing, managing and monitoring the non-refundable financing contract, reporting the results and submitting the supporting documents for achieving the object of the non-refundable financing contract, carrying out quantitative and qualitative studies in order to evaluate the effects and impact of the project. Transfer of personal data: These personal data between data operators and third parties can be transmitted within the European Economic Area, especially on the territory of Romania, Belgium, Hungary, Bulgaria, Austria. In addition, these personal data may be transferred to the following categories of persons: financier, evaluators and/or auditors on the occasion of the controls carried out by them at the request of the financier, tax authorities and other public authorities in case of a potential control on their part. I understand and agree that I will not receive any monetary or other compensation for these photos/videos or recordings. The policy regarding the processing of personal data can be consulted at: <https://gdpr.eu/>

Nature FIRST

Nature FIRST focuses on biodiversity monitoring, tackling key challenges such as 1) enabling near real-time monitoring, 2) detecting changes and trends early, and 3) turning predictions into timely, actionable interventions.

We achieve this by combining remote sensing technologies (both satellite-based and on-site) with environmental forensics, which extracts insights from field evidence. This helps us uncover cause-effect relations and prevent wildlife and environmental crimes. By integrating these sciences into digital twins—virtual copies of ecosystems—we shift from periodic mapping to real-time monitoring, enabling proactive interventions based on forecasted trends.

We are testing this approach in four nature reserves across five countries: Ancares-Courel (Spain), Danube Delta (Romania), Maramures Transboundary Area (Romania/Ukraine), and Stara Planina Mountain (Bulgaria). These sites, home to vulnerable species like bears and wolves and iconic species like pelicans and sturgeons, face common challenges such as habitat loss, fires, human-wildlife conflicts, and poaching.

Nature FIRST is pioneering the use of digital twin technology for conservation. Our solutions are available early in the project, and we encourage Natura 2000 managers, researchers, policy-makers, and other stakeholders to reach out for more information.

In alignment with the Tusnad EcoBear Conference, which addresses human-large carnivore coexistence, Nature FIRST supports this event to strengthen conservation efforts and promote strategies for reducing human-wildlife conflicts.

Learn more about the project on our website:

<https://www.naturefirst.info/>

Program

Monday – 21 October

18:00 Welcome

18:00 - 19:30 **Documentary - Bears Uncovered: Crisis**
Discussion with the director: Ovidiu Stancu

Tuesday – 22 October

8:00 - 09:30 Registration

09:30 - 10:00 **Conference opening and introduction (EN/RO)**

Session 1 – Fostering ecological connectivity

10:00 - 10:25 **Cristian Papp: Can ecological connectivity support human-large carnivore coexistence?**

10:25 - 10:50 **Ancuța Fedorca: IUCN-WCPA Connectivity Conservation Specialist Group: A global network dedicated to ecological connectivity**

10:50 - 11:05 Marius Costin Nistorescu: Bears don't cross here

11:05 - 11:20 László Demeter: Spatial coverage of the Natura 2000 network and site management effects on bear conservation in the Eastern Carpathians

Session 2 – Wildlife forensics

11:20 - 11:50 **Claire Gwinnett: Sherlock Holmes and the Bear Poaching Case**

11:50 - 12:30 **Coffee break**

Session 3 – Integrating technology in conflict reduction

12:30 - 13:00 **Boris Hinojo: Habitat mapping and its contribution to human-bear coexistence in the Băile Tușnad region, Romania**

13:00 - 13:20 Jan Kees Schakel: Caught in the Camera Trap: Navigating the myriad of options

13:20 - 13:35 Cosmin-Andrei Conțu: RO-BEAR: Monitor and report bear sightings

13:35 - 13:50 Albin Ahmeti: A species conservation simulation system based on knowledge graph for brown bear movement prediction

13:50 - 14:05 Jan Kees Schakel: Bear Habitat Suitability Maps: Introduction of a novel and cost-effective mapping approach

14:05 - 15:30 **Lunch break**

Session 3A – Developing bear-smart communities

- 15:30 - 16:00 **Michal Haring: Bear resistant solutions in Slovakia**
- 16:00 - 16:15 Alexandra Sallay-Moşoi: Technical overview of the bear-smart community of Băile Tuşnad, Romania
- 16:15 - 16:30 Robin Rigg: Sharing knowledge and experience of living with bears
- 16:30 - 16:45 Mihai I. Pop: Bear in Mind the System. Policy vs. Politics in Romania
- 16:45 - 17:00 Levente Dósa: Human and bear interaction on the Csomád volcano. A brief history and 2024 follow up
- 17:00 - 17:15 Júlia Janka Faller: Assessing market dynamics and financial constraints in relation to data-driven biodiversity monitoring: Insights from the Horizon Europe Nature FIRST Project
- 17:15 - 17:30 Cristian Valeriu Maloş: Coexistence through sustainable outdoor activities

Session 4 – Posters

- 17:30 - 17:40 María Párraga: Improving key food resources and preventing winter conflicts for Cantabrian brown bear under climate change scenarios
- 17:40 - 17:50 Ilya Acosta-Pankov: Human-bear conflict recorded with the Cluey app in a pilot site: A preliminary study on the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) in Bulgaria
- 17:50 - 18:00 Vladimir Todorov: Human disturbance to the brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) winter dens

18:00 - 19:30 Panel discussion - From Conflict to Coexistence: The Role of advanced technology in preventing human-wildlife conflicts

19:30 Reception and wine-tasting with Somelier Robert-Claudiu Bentea

Wednesday – 23 October

8:00 - 09:30 Registration

Session 3B – Developing bear-smart communities

- 09:30 - 10:00 **Anna Davison: The human-bear conflict radar: a digital twin to monitor and predict conflicts with brown bear (*Ursus arctos*) in Bulgaria**
- 10:00 - 10:15 Aleksandar Dutsov: Human-bear conflict in a depopulating mountain region – social and environmental factors
- 10:15 - 10:30 Romana Uhrinová: Carnivore tracking project: a way to coexistence with large carnivores via a volunteer involvement
- 10:30 - 10:45 László Gál: The garbage bears of Băile Tuşnad. A study of habituation in Romanian brown bears
- 10:45 - 11:00 Claudiu Olenici: Empowering wildlife conservation: The NGO's role in supporting authorities with a feasible, complementary response and awareness system - prototype
- 11:00 - 11:30 **Dávid Sütő, Alexandra Sallay-Moşoi: Modern misbeliefs about large carnivores influencing human-wildlife conflict**

11:30 - 12:00 Coffee break

Session 4A – Managing human-large carnivore conflicts

- 12:00 - 12:30 **Robin Rigg: Bear attacks on humans: patterns, drivers and prevention**
12:30 - 12:45 Nick Thorpe: Reporting and misreporting bears
12:45 - 13:00 Roman Cherepanyn: Structure and dynamics of conflicts with large carnivores in the Ukrainian Carpathians
13:00 - 13:30 **Jenny Anne Glikman: Human-bear coexistence and protected areas in Central-Appennines**
13:30 - 13:45 Andra-Claudia Neagu: Insufficient scientific evidence hinders large carnivore management in Romania
13:45 - 14:00 Thomas Paulic: Hunting principles for contributing to sustainable management and conservation of large carnivores in countries with high human-wildlife conflicts
14:00 - 14:15 Niki Voumvoulaki: Bear – motorways conflicts in Greece. Operational and maintenance challenges in Egnatia Odos S.A. case

14:15 - 15:45 Lunch break

Session 4B – Managing human-large carnivore conflicts

- 15:45 - 16:15 **Tibor Hartel: Human-bear conflicts in Romania: social polarization and conservation challenges**
16:15 - 16:30 José Vicente Lopez-Bao: Human-bear coexistence in the Cantabrian Mountains: prevention and mitigation of conflicts
16:30 - 16:45 Vukan Lavadinović: Attitudes of Serbian hunters toward large carnivores
16:45 - 17:00 Andrea Sólyom: The bears' appearance in a regional and a national newspaper in the first half of 2024
17:00 - 17:15 Radu Mot: Preventing and combating poaching – conclusions and recommendations after the implementation of the LIFE Connect Carpathians project
17:15 - 17:30 Silvia Borlea: Updated permeability and infrastructure conflict map of Romania
17:30 - 17:45 Horea-Emil Petrehuş: The importance of human management in the natural area of Romania
17:45 - 18:00 Laurent Schley: The return of the wolf: lucky stroke or surplus to requirements?
18:00 - 19:30 **Documentary - Bears Uncovered: Solutions (discussion with the director: Ovidiu Stancu)**

19:30 Reception

Contents

Tuesday 22 October	
Session 1: Fostering ecological connectivity	12
Cristian Papp, Călin Ardelean, Ioana Ismail: Can ecological connectivity support human-large carnivore coexistence?	12
Ancuța Fedorca, Aaron Laur, Gary Tabor, Gabriel Oppler: IUCN-WCPA Connectivity Conservation Specialist Group: A global network dedicated to ecological connectivity	13
Cristina Băncilă, Silvia Borlea, Alexandra Doba, <u>Marius Nistorescu</u> : Bears don't cross here	14
László Demeter: Spatial coverage of the Natura 2000 network and site management effects on bear conservation in the Eastern Carpathians	15
Tuesday 22 October	
Session 2: Wildlife forensics	16
Claire Gwinnett: Sherlock Holmes and the Bear Poaching Case	16
Tuesday 22 October	
Session 3: Integrating technology in conflict reduction	17
Yago Alonso, Federico Cheda, Marco Rubinos, <u>Boris Hinojo</u> , Alexandra Sallay-Moșoi, Nándor Erős, Cristian Papp: Habitat mapping and its contribution to human-bear coexistence in the Băile Tușnad region, Romania	17
Jan Kees Schakel: Caught in the Camera Trap: Navigating the myriad of options	18
Cosmin-Andrei Coțu: RO-BEAR: Monitor and report bear sightings	19
<u>Albin Ahmeti</u> , Robert David, Artem Revenko, Jan-Kees Schakel: A species conservation simulation system based on knowledge graph for brown bear movement prediction	20
<u>Jan Kees Schakel</u> , Koen de Koning , Melanie Arp : Bear Habitat Suitability Maps: Introduction of a novel and cost-effective mapping approach	21
Tuesday 22 October	
Session 3A: Developing bear-smart communities	22
Michal Haring: Bear resistant solutions in Slovakia	22

<u>Alexandra Sallay-Moşoi, László Gál, Nándor Erős, Cristian Papp:</u> Technical overview of the bear-smart community of Băile Tuşnad, Romania	23
<u>Robin Rigg, Andrea Besinic, Micha Herdtfelder, Daniel Mettler, Silvia Ribeiro, Valeria Salvatori, John Linnell:</u> Sharing knowledge and experience of living with bears	24
<u>Mihai I. Pop, Robert Szép, Silviu Chiriac:</u> Bear in Mind the System. Policy vs. Politics in Romania	25
<u>Levente Dósa:</u> Human and bear interaction on the Csomád volcano. A brief history and 2024 follow up	26
<u>Júlia Janka Faller, Linda van Duivenbode:</u> Assessing market dynamics and financial constraints in relation to data-driven biodiversity monitoring: Insights from the Horizon Europe Nature FIRST Project	27
<u>Cristian Valeriu Maloş, Tibor Hartel, Cristian Remus Papp, Ionuţ Pascu, Oana David:</u> Coexistence through sustainable outdoor activities	28
Tuesday 22 October	
Session 4: Posters	29
<u>María Párraga, Guillermo Palomero:</u> Improving key food resources and preventing winter conflicts for Cantabrian brown bear under climate change scenarios	29
<u>Ilya Acosta-Pankov, Vladimir Todorov, Nikola Doykin, Nikola Ganchev, Jan Kees Schakel, Aleksander Dutsov:</u> Human-bear conflict recorded with the Cluey app in a pilot site: a preliminary study on the brown bear (<i>Ursus arctos</i>) in Bulgaria	30
<u>Vladimir Todorov, Venislava Spasova:</u> Human disturbance to the brown bear (<i>Ursus arctos</i>) winter dens	31
Wednesday 23 October	
Session 3B: Developing bear-smart communities	32
<u>Anna Davison, Koen de Koning, Jan Kees Schakel, Vladimir Todorov, Melanie Arp, Nikola Doykin, Ilya Acosta:</u> The human-bear conflict radar: a digital twin to monitor and predict conflicts with brown bear (<i>Ursus arctos</i>) in Bulgaria	32
<u>Aleksandar Dutsov, Nikola Ganchev, Joost de Jong, Vladimir Todorov, Maria Kachamakova, Georgi Georgiev:</u> Human-bear conflict in a depopulating mountain region — social and environmental factors	33
<u>Romana Uhrinová:</u> Carnivore Tracking Project: a way to coexistence with large carnivores via a volunteer involvement	34
<u>László Gál, Írisz-Barbara Dobos, István Maák:</u> The garbage bears of Băile Tuşnad. A study of habitation in Romanian brown bears	35
<u>Claudiu Olenici:</u> Empowering wildlife conservation: The NGO's role in supporting authorities with a feasible, complementary response and awareness system - prototype	36
<u>Dávid Sütő, Alexandra Sallay-Moşoi:</u> Modern misbeliefs about large carnivores influencing human-wildlife conflict	37

Wednesday 23 October	
Session 4A: Managing human-large carnivore conflicts	38
Robin Rigg:	
Bear attacks on humans: patterns, drivers and prevention	38
Nick Thorpe:	
Reporting and misreporting bears	39
Roman Cherepanyn, Taras Yamelynets:	
Structure and dynamics of conflicts with large carnivores in the Ukrainian Carpathians	40
Jenny Anne Glikman, Maria Benciolini, Cloe Mirenda, Beatrice Frank:	
Human-bear coexistence and protected areas in Central-Appennines	41
Andra-Claudia Neagu , Laurentiu Rozyłowicz :	
Insufficient scientific evidence hinders large carnivore management in Romania	42
Thomas Paulic:	
Hunting principles for contributing to sustainable management and conservation of large carnivores in countries with high human-wildlife conflicts	43
Lazaros Georgiadis, Niki Voumvoulaki:	
Bear -- motorways conflicts in Greece. Operational and maintenance challenges in Egnatia Odos S.A. case	44
Wednesday 23 October	
Session 4B: Managing human-large carnivore conflicts	45
Tibor Hartel:	
Human-bear conflicts in Romania: social polarization and conservation challenges	45
José Vicente Lopez-Bao , María Párraga , Noa González , Guillermo Palomero :	
Human-bear coexistence in the Cantabrian Mountains: prevention and mitigation of conflicts	46
Vukan Lavadinović, Dejan Beuković , Zoran Popović , Miroslava Polovinski-Horvatović , Nikola Mihajlović :	
Attitudes of serbian hunters toward large carnivores	47
Andrea Sólyom:	
The bears' appearance in a regional and a national newspaper in the first half of 2024	48
Radu Mot:	
Preventing and combating poaching – conclusions and recommendations after the implementation of the LIFE Connect Carpathians project	49
Silvia Borlea, Marius Nistorescu, Alexandra Doba, Radu Mot:	
Updated permeability and infrastructure conflict map of Romania	50
Horea-Emil Petrehuş:	
The importance of human management in the natural areal of Romania	51
Laurent Schley:	
The return of the wolf: lucky stroke or surplus to requirements?	52
Index of Authors	53

Structure and dynamics of conflicts with large carnivores in the Ukrainian Carpathians

23 Oct
2024
12:45

Roman Cherepanyn^{1,2*}, Taras Yamelynets^{1,3}

¹ WWF-Ukraine (Public Union World Wide Fund for Nature Ukraine), 4 Raisy Okipnoi Str., office 170, Kyiv, 02002, Ukraine

² Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Biology and Ecology Department, 201 b Halytska Str., Ivano-Frankivsk, 76000, Ukraine

³ Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Faculty of Geography, 41 Doroshenka Str., Lviv, 79000, Ukraine

*e-mail: rcherepanyn@wwf.ua

Conflicts between large carnivores and humans are common in the Carpathians. Stakeholder attention to the study and management of conflicts has increased significantly worldwide. But in Ukraine, the topic of the coexistence of humans and large carnivores, as well as the consequences of such interaction, has not received enough attention. We have focused only on conflicts between farmers/beekeepers and large carnivores (*Canis lupus* – grey wolf, *Ursus arctos* – brown bear, *Lynx lynx* – Eurasian lynx) in the Ukrainian Carpathians in this analysis. The following model territories were: Verkhovyna, Nadvirna, Kalush, and Kolomyia districts of the Ivano-Frankivsk region; Rakhiv, Khust, and Tyachiv districts of the Zakarpattia region; Stryi district of the Lviv region. 115 locations were selected (91 farms and 24 apiaries). An annual survey method focusing on the types, locations and consequences of conflicts was implemented from 2018 to 2023. The data were processed in Excel, a package of online programs from the Sensing Clues platform and ESRI ArcGIS Pro 3.2.2 license software. In 2018, 51.64% of farmers faced wolf attacks on their livestock, in 2023 – 6.59%. In 2018, 16.48% of farmers faced lynx attacks on their livestock, in 2023 – 2.20%. In 2018, 15.38% of farmers faced bear attacks on their livestock, in 2023 – 2.20%. In 2018, the share of conflicts in apiaries with a bear was 29.16%, in 2023 – 16.77%. In 2018, wolves killed/injured 225 domestic animals, in 2023 – 16; in 2018, lynxes killed/injured 27 domestic animals, in 2023 – 4; in 2018, bears killed/injured 38 domestic animals, destroyed 107 beehives, in 2023 – 2 domestic animals, 13 beehives. The structure and dynamics of conflicts between large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers on model territories in the Ukrainian Carpathians from 2018 to 2023 have been established. The number and negative consequences of conflicts between large carnivores and farmers/beekeepers are decreasing, which probably is related to the increasing use of electric fences for conflict prevention (from 0 in 2018 to 23.08% in 2023 among researched farmers and from 0 in 2018 to 75% in 2023 among researched beekeepers) and the increasing of the pastoral dogs to protect livestock among farmers, who do not have conflicts with large carnivores and use dogs against large carnivore attacks (from 3.29% in 2018 to 20.88% in 2023).

Index of Authors

- Acosta-Pankov
Ilya, 30
- Ahmeti
Albin, 20
- Borlea
Silvia, 50
- Cherepanyn
Roman, 40
- Conțu
Cosmin-Andrei, 19
- Davison
Anna, 32
- Demeter
László, 15
- Dutsov
Aleksandar, 33
- Dósa
Levente, 26
- Faller
Júlia Janka, 27
- Fedorca
Ancuța, 13
- Georgiadis
Lazaros, 44
- Glikman
Jenny Anne, 41
- Gwinnett
Claire, 16
- Gál
László, 35
- Haring
Michal, 22
- Hartel
Tibor, 45
- Hinojo
Boris, 17
- Lavadinović
Vukan, 47
- Lopez-Bao
José Vicente, 46
- Maloș
Cristian Valeriu, 28
- Mot
Radu, 49
- Neagu
Andra-Claudia, 42
- Nistorescu
Marius Costin, 14
- Olenici
Claudiu, 36
- Papp
Cristian, 12
- Paulic
Thomas, 43
- Petrehuș
Horea-Emil, 51
- Pop
Mihai, 25
- Párraga
María, 29
- Rigg
Robin, 24, 38
- Sallay-Moșoi
Alexandra, 23
- Schakel
Jan Kees, 18, 21
- Schley
Laurent, 52
- Sólyom
Andrea, 48
- Sütő
Dávid, 37
- Thorpe
Nick, 39
- Todorov
Vladimir, 31
- Uhrinová
Romana, 34

